

Policy Values of Technological Innovation Support Policies for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises : South Korean Stakeholder Differences and Consensus

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Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) play a crucial role in the South Korean economy, and policies supporting their technological innovation are of significant importance. Despite substantial government efforts in this regard, opinions on the efficiency and values underlying these policies vary. This study examines the policy values shaping technological innovation support policies for SMEs and explores stakeholder differences and consensus. Drawing on conflicting values such as excellence vs. universality, autonomy vs. accountability, and economic effects vs. publicness, the research analyzes responses from 51 stakeholders, including SMEs, university researchers, research institution researchers, and government officials. The findings reveal divergent perceptions among stakeholders, emphasizing the value-based policy redesign to better support technological innovation in SMEs.

1. Introduction

In South Korea, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) play a dominant role, constituting 99.9% of businesses and employing 82.7% of the workforce (Korea Federation of Small and Medium Business, 2021), significantly impacting the economy. The imperative challenge lies in fostering technological innovation and growth among SMEs, which possess the agility to navigate innovative technologies and markets, offering advantages over larger corporations. Collaborating with public research institutions positions SMEs as pivotal contributors to the commercialization of public knowledge (Baumol, 2002).

Examining the distinct characteristics of Research and Development (R&D), a quintessential technological innovation activity, reveals its non-specific outcomes compared to other business activities. Challenges include a substantial time lag from result creation to product materialization, uncertainty about potential rewards, and considerable resource costs (Kay, 1988). While larger corporations can overcome these challenges with abundant resources, SMEs, constrained by limited resources, may exhibit passivity in technological innovation. Leaving technological innovation solely to market forces may shrink SMEs' R&D activities, leading to market failure and a failure to secure nationally essential technologies due to underinvestment.

Acknowledging the positive role of government support in overcoming market failures and achieving efficient resource redistribution is evident in numerous studies (Correa, Andrés & Borja-Vega, 2013; Negassi & Sattin, 2014; Gaillard-Ladinska, Non & Straathof, 2015). In South Korea, the significance of policies supporting technological innovation in SMEs is underscored by various support programs. Government R&D projects have seen substantial investment, reaching KRW 4,971 billion in SME-led projects by 2021, with a 10.1% annual growth rate since 2012 (Ministry of Science and ICT & Korea Institute of S&T Evaluation and Planning, 2022). This annual growth rate surpasses all other research performers. Indirect financial support through tax expenditures, including research and workforce development tax deductions, amounted to KRW 1,293.3 billion in 2021, consistently increasing over the past decade. Combining these figures, the annual direct and indirect financial support for SMEs' technological innovation totals KRW 6,265.4 billion. While reflecting the government's keen

interest in SMEs' technological innovation, this substantial financial support raises questions about its efficiency and desirability.

Government policy support relies on publicly funded resources, emphasizing challenges in investment efficiency with expanding support. Allocating limited resources and choosing between conflicting alternatives in policy program operation remains a central issue in policy decision-making.

Policy decision-making, akin to all human decision-making, is closely tied to value judgments. Values, encompassing preferences, pursuits, wishes, etc., influence the policy decision-making process significantly (Firth, 1998; Berlin, 2002). Despite the lack of systematic analysis in the academic domain, this study aims to quantitatively analyze current and aspired values in SMEs' technological innovation support policies, recognizing differing stakeholder perceptions.

2. Literature Review and Research Issues

2.1. Technological Innovation Support Policy for SMEs

The South Korean government has implemented diverse policies, including subsidies, tax incentives, and workforce development, to bolster technological innovation in SMEs and prevent the contraction of innovation activities due to risks. In 2021, funds allocated to SMEs from the national R&D budget totaled 5.0 trillion won, complemented by approximately 1.3 trillion won through research and workforce development tax deductions (Ministry of Science and ICT & Korea Institute of S&T Evaluation and Planning, 2022). Government research funding for SMEs has seen an average annual increase of 10.1% over the past decade, surpassing other research performers. Despite this substantial support, concerns about policy efficiency have emerged.

Analysis of 24 prior studies critiquing policies supporting technological innovation in Korean SMEs identified 110 criticisms, revealing recurrent issues (Jin & Kim, 2023). Primary concerns include a lack of clarity in mission and roles among government ministries, inadequate coordination of organizational functions (17 criticisms), inappropriate methods or criteria for performance evaluation (15 criticisms), insufficient support for collaborative R&D projects in open innovation (14 criticisms), and unbalanced resource allocation biased towards specific sectors or entities (10 criticisms). Such criticisms are often raised not as issues of objective facts but due to differences in stakeholders' perceptions of policy values. Therefore, it is necessary to systematically analyze the differences and consensus in policy values among stakeholders in the context of supporting technological innovation for SMEs.

2.2. Stakeholders and Policy Value

Values, broadly defined as emotions, preferences, and wishes towards a subject (Firth, 1998), take on a different dimension in policy. Policy values encapsulate the desirable state sought through policies, embodying societal aspirations (Stewart, 2009; Jørgensen & Bozeman, 2007). Functioning as an ideology, policy values propel public policies within specific contexts (Ighodalo, 2019). Influenced by individual subjectivity, understanding policy values requires stakeholder perspectives.

Stakeholders, broadly defined as individuals or groups with interests or losses concerning specific issues, play a pivotal role in policy dynamics (Freeman, 2010). The exploration by Oldenhof, Wehrens & Bal (2022) into conflicts during preliminary policy experimentation identified two key conflict patterns: the politics of power and conflicting goals. Empirical analyses reveal competitive dynamics among groups based on priorities, approaches, and orientations within a trust system (Sabatier & Jenkins-Smith, 1993). Each stakeholder's values represent a rational choice within their organization, yet this rationality is subjective

and instrumental (Jung, 2003). Consequently, variations in value prioritization between organizations lead to conflicts (Ettelt, Mays & Allen, 2015).

Despite recognizing the significance of value conflicts as drivers of policy change, there is a lack of systematic clarification regarding differences in policy values among stakeholders in technological innovation support policies for SMEs. Consequently, there is a crucial need for an analysis delving into stakeholder perceptions of current policy values and determining the values policies should aim for in the future. This sets the stage for formulating essential research questions to guide the exploration of stakeholder perspectives on the underlying values of existing policies and the aspired values for future policy directions. Thus, the following research questions can be formulated:

- ♦ Q1. (Current Value) What are the current underlying policy values of policies supporting technological innovation for SMEs?
- ♦ Q2. (Aspired Value) What values should policies supporting technological innovation for SMEs aim in the future?

3. Method

We presented three pairs of conflicting policy values targeting key stakeholders in policies supporting technological innovation in SMEs. We quantitatively investigated the perception of the currently prioritized foundational values and the values that should be pursued in the future among these stakeholders. The types, concepts, and indicators of policy values below were established through a review of extensive prior research and a Focus Group Interview (FGI) involving 11 academic experts (Table 1).

Table 1. Operational Definition of Values and Key Indicators for Survey

Type	Policy value	Definition
Design value 1	Excellence	<p>“Boldly support the selection of top-tier companies”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identify high-capacity companies and provide strategic focused support. ● Evaluate projects based on technological and commercial excellence.
	Universality	<p>“Provide universal opportunities to as many companies as possible”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Support the accumulation of potential innovation experiences and capabilities. ● Expand opportunities for universal project participation targeting marginalized sectors, regions, and companies.
Design value 2	Autonomy	<p>“Ensure researcher autonomy to promote innovation”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Flexibility in establishing and modifying research plans. ● Grant autonomy in research budget execution and relax control. ● Autonomous research management by research leaders within companies.
	Accountability	<p>“Uphold policy transparency and social responsibility”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Stringency and transparency in the research execution process. ● Adherence to public financial principles in research budget execution. ● Rational research management following formal regulations.
Outcome value	Economic effect	<p>“Create the highest economic value”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Companies develop innovative products and services through government technological innovation support to maximize economic impact. ● Emphasize return on investment (ROI).
	Publicity	<p>“Let’s develop technologies essential to our society”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Prioritize support for the development of technologies in fields deemed crucial for social and public welfare by the government. ● Ensure that the outcomes of technological development extend beyond the scope of specific companies, spreading across society as a whole.

The stakeholders targeted for the survey are broadly categorized into four types: industry, academia, research institutions, and government. While individual diversity in values can be further identified within each type of group, for the sake of practicality in the survey, specific target groups were set as follows: employees of SMEs, university-affiliated researchers, researchers affiliated with research institutions, and government officials. A total of 154 individuals with high expertise and understanding of policies were carefully selected and invited to participate in the survey, with 51 responses collected and analyzed (Table 2).

Table 2. The Survey Response Status by Stakeholder Type

Type	Survey Participants	Responses Collected	Response Rate
Total	154	51	33.1
SMEs	91	20	22.0
University	15	10	66.7
Research Institutions	18	10	55.6
Government	30	11	36.7

The survey questions focused on a paired comparison between conflicting values concerning the current perception of policy values and aspirational orientation. Using a 9-point scale, where equal importance between two values is rated as 1 point and a specific policy being significantly more important is rated as 9 points, the respondents were asked to provide their responses. During the survey, a paired comparison format was used, ranging from -9 to +9. However, the reporting of results was converted to a positive scale from 1 to 17. In this context, the neutral score between the two values is 9 points.

This design aimed to ascertain their perception of the relative importance of contrasting values. Specifically, for three contrasting scenarios, the survey investigated the level of awareness regarding the current importance of values and opinions on aspirational goals separately. The design facilitates the derivation of conclusions regarding which values are currently considered important and which ones should be pursued in the future.

4. Result

The survey results reveal follows insights (Figure 1). Firstly, respondents broadly agree on the need to shift policy values from universality to excellence in supporting targets. The average difference between current and aspired states is 2.9, signifying a clear consensus. Stakeholder groups—SMEs, university researchers, and research institute researchers—show statistically significant recognition of the necessity to move towards excellence. Government officials acknowledge this shift but believe the current policy already embodies excellence to a significant extent.

Secondly, in the realm of administrative management, stakeholders unanimously advocate for strengthening autonomy over accountability. The average perception across all respondents underscores a shift from accountability (10.4) to autonomy (7.1) in current values. Statistically significant differences among SMEs, research institutions, and government officials indicate a strong consensus on prioritizing autonomy. Research institute researchers particularly emphasize autonomy, aligning with existing policy discourse. Interestingly, SMEs, though stressing autonomy in R&D, exhibit a balanced emphasis on autonomy and accountability. These results suggest that the companies selected as survey respondents representing SMEs in this survey are relatively high in technological innovation capabilities and engagement. In other words, these companies, based on higher levels of innovation capabilities compared to typical SMEs, critically view lower-level enterprises that overly rely on autonomy.

Thirdly, regarding conflicting values in technology innovation support policies for SMEs, stakeholders lean towards publicity over economic effects. Although there's an opinion that values should shift slightly towards publicity, current perceptions and aspirational orientations show no significant differences. While all stakeholders, except SMEs, believe publicness should be emphasized more, only government officials exhibit a statistically significant difference. SMEs perceive a balanced focus on economic effects and publicity, suggesting a prioritization of immediate economic benefits over broader societal values. This quantitative response aligns with the common-sense inference about SMEs prioritizing products and services for immediate gains rather than emphasizing socially impactful outcomes.

Figure 1. Perceived Gap in Current and Aspired Policy Values by Stakeholder (Visualization)

5. Conclusion and Implications

Respondents prioritize accountability over autonomy and economic effects over publicness in shaping the underlying values of the current policy. They perceive a balance between excellence and universality in the current situation. However, differences among stakeholders are observed. University researchers emphasize universality, while government officials respond with a focus on excellence in the conflict between excellence and universality. In the conflict between economic effects and publicness, companies recognize publicness more significantly than government officials, who respond with a policy designed around economic effects.

Regarding the aspired values to be pursued in the future, there is a unanimous opinion among all stakeholders that the policy, currently balanced between universality and excellence, should shift towards excellence. In the conflict between accountability and autonomy, there is a consensus that the center of gravity, currently leaning towards accountability, should shift towards autonomy. On the issue of conflicting values between economic effects and publicness, opinions are varied, with a general inclination towards emphasizing publicness more than the current state. However, this inclination is led by government officials, and other stakeholders, particularly SMEs, emphasize a slight shift towards economic effects.

The limitations of this survey include its focus on specific opposing value scenarios, a relatively small number of respondents, and potential bias in the selection of SMEs participants. Despite these limitations, the survey provides meaningful insights into the conflicting policy values in the area of SMEs technology innovation support policy. The results highlight the quantitative differences in the perception of policy values among different stakeholder groups, offering valuable considerations for future policy discourse. The analysis can serve as a reference for constructing a constructive policy discourse, taking into account the differences in perspectives among various stakeholder types in shaping the developmental direction of this policy area.

Open science practices

The data used in this study is exclusively obtained and held by the author, and it can be disclosed upon a valid request.

Competing interests

The author asserts that there is no conflict of interest in this paper.

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